

The Historical Development of Television: From Its Early Stages to the Digital Era

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Abstract. This article focuses on the historical development of television in Uzbekistan, starting from its early steps in the 1950s to the transition to the digital era. The process of establishing television in the country is discussed, from the first regular broadcasts in Tashkent in 1956 to the creation and adaptation of popular television programs such as "Fathers Speak—Eye of Wisdom" and "Television Miniature Theater." The contribution of notable figures like Elbek Musaev and Karim Maksudkhodzhayev in shaping television culture is highlighted, as well as the steps leading to the introduction of color television in 1977. The article emphasizes the role of television as a powerful tool of mass communication, shaping public consciousness and strengthening national identity in the post-Soviet period. Additionally, it discusses the impact of digitalization on the current trends in television development and its ongoing significance in society.

Keywords: television, digitalization, mass communication, national identity, television programs, operators, technology, development of technologies.

Throughout history, many great inventions and discoveries have paved the way for new stages of progress. People, unable to overcome vast distances in a short time, have long dreamed of traveling far and staying updated on world events. In the 1950s, the formation of television in Uzbekistan began. By the 1960s, television creators had mastered the technical possibilities of the medium, producing television programs that met the needs and expectations of the people. Inspired by ancient Eastern wisdom, famous shows like "Fathers Speak—Eye of Wisdom" (1962) and "Television Miniature Theater" (1963) made Uzbek television one of the most popular in the world.

The well-known Uzbek artist and cultural figure, Elbek Musaev, recalls: "Television entered our lives swiftly, and each day, both our inspiration and experience grew. We aimed for greater and better achievements. In 1962, we adapted Chinghiz Aitmatov's story 'The First Teacher' for television. Taking into account all the specificities of events occurring in various time periods and complex situations, we understood the challenging nature of this task."

The construction of the television center in Tashkent began in 1954. Regular broadcasts in Tashkent started on November 5, 1956. Initially, the studio included four editorial departments: social-political, musical, literary-dramatic, and children's programming. In 1958, the first mobile television station in Tashkent was launched. In 1963, the first television link between Tashkent, Alma-Ata, and Bishkek was established. From 1965, broadcasts of All-Union television programs began in Uzbekistan, and in 1967, Uzbekistan started airing its own programs on a separate channel. Television became a vital tool of mass communication and a social institution in Uzbekistan from the 1960s. The country led the Soviet Republics in terms of television ownership and the development of telecommunication networks.

In 1956, with the launch of the Tashkent TV studio, experienced media professionals, including Karim Maksudkhodzhayev, became involved in the process. He became widely known as the chief operator of Uzbek television, continuing to develop his creative and technical skills by shooting and producing numerous popular TV programs and documentaries. Television, as a synthetic art form,

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differed from cinema and theater in its universality and its ability to impact audiences at any time and place. During the 1960s, television became increasingly accessible to viewers, and its audience grew year by year. This period also marked significant progress in the professionalization of television operators and program creators.

In 1977, the launch of color television expanded the possibilities of the medium. That same year, the first Uzbek color video film "Qutlug' Khan" (directed by M. Makhkamov) was released, marking a significant event in the history of Uzbek television.

After Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, television continued to evolve, with the creation of new channels and improved transmission quality. The development of technologies and digital television opened new horizons for more effective and large-scale audience engagement.

Television became a powerful communication tool offering a wide range of programs, from entertainment and art to educational and informational content.

Television, as one of the most significant forms of mass communication, played a crucial role in the socio-cultural development of Uzbekistan. Since its inception in the country in 1956, it has not only been a source of information but also a powerful instrument for education and upbringing, as well as a symbol of progress and modernization. Key milestones in the development of Uzbek television include the introduction of color television, the creation of numerous popular programs and films, and the increased accessibility of television to the masses.

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan continued to actively develop television, incorporating new technologies, expanding networks, and increasing the number of broadcasting channels. This has contributed not only to cultural exchange but also to strengthening national identity. Modern technologies and digitalization offer new possibilities for the continued growth of television in Uzbekistan, making it an integral part of everyday life for citizens and an important factor in shaping public consciousness.

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